

A WATER HEATER THAT IS DESIGNED FOR SELF-REGULATION IN SOLAR HEATING SYSTEMS.

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Abstract: *A new calculation method has been developed for water distribution systems with a constant cross-section that are uniformly perforated along their height. This method can be applied to multilayer, stratified thermal storage tanks used for solar heating and hot water supply.*

Keywords: *Water distribution, heat storage, solar heating system, thermal energy storage.*

INTRODUCTION

Solar water heaters are the most common and cost-effective way to use solar energy to heat water. They have the highest efficiency at converting sunlight into heat, which is needed throughout the year for hot water. Knowing the habits of family members helps calculate their daily usage and the total usage of the family. In Europe, one person uses about 50-70 liters of hot water per day, with an average temperature of 45°C. However, in Ukraine, many people don't conserve hot water, so their usage may be higher, requiring more thermal energy for heating a larger volume of water. It takes at least 3.65 kWh of energy per day for each person, totaling more than 109 kWh for a family of four per month.

RELEVANCE

Water heat accumulators (WHA) are an essential part of solar energy systems (SES). They help to align the time of heat production and consumption between the solar collectors (SC) and the consumers: hot water supplies (HWS) and heating systems. The water heat accumulator can operate with significant temperature stratification, where the top of the tank is hotter than the bottom [1].

The principle of layered charging of a heat accumulator with an SC, where water heated in the collector is fed to a layer corresponding to its temperature along the length of the tank, and the mixing of layers is avoided, is widely used in the design of solar HWS and heating systems [2].

At the same time, the potential gain in solar energy coverage for a solar installation with a perfectly stratified tank and a low specific water flow through SC, in the range of 0.002-0.07 kg/(m²·s), compared to a fully mixed tank with a large specific flow through the solar collector, can be about 1/3 of that [1].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The development of a new design for a water heat accumulator that utilizes natural stratification to prevent mixing of hot and cold water is underway. The accumulator has been designed to be self-regulating, meaning it can operate without

external controls.

The design incorporates the principles of natural stratification. This means that hot water will rise to the top of the tank, while cold water sinks to the bottom, creating a stable flow within the accumulator and maintaining consistent water temperature.

To achieve this goal, the design utilizes a system based on Archimedes' principle, which creates a volumetric force pushing the hot water upward and the cold water downward. This ensures the water remains separated into hot and cold compartments, preventing mixing. This innovative approach to water heating has been developed based on an analysis of existing designs and criteria for stable stratified flow within the tank. By eliminating the need for mixing, this new design offers a more efficient and reliable solution for heating and cooling systems.

The German companies, Viessmann [2] and Buderus [3], have developed special variants of their products using special HWS equipment with automatic temperature control for heating mountain water in the SC. To do this, they use layer-by-layer charging WHA. Therefore, the development of thermal battery designs that ensure a high temperature stratification in storage tanks is a crucial task that needs to be addressed.

When using the principle of layered charging, water heated in the IC is distributed in layers, each with a certain temperature. At the same time, there is no mixing with colder layers.

When charging a capacitive water heater with an integrated heat exchanger, without using the layered principle, the entire volume of the liquid is simultaneously heated. To achieve the required temperature, the collector must operate for a long period of time. If a need for heat occurs before the required water temperature has been reached, then additional heating will be required using a conventional heat generator.

With layer-by-layer charging, set temperature in the upper part of the capacitive water heater is reached earlier. The entire volume reaches set temperature within the same period of time as a water heater without layer-by-layer charging.

The work of many foreign solar engineers, has been devoted to the study of issues related to the phenomenon of stratification of water in battery tanks in relation to solar heat supply systems [4, 5].

The action of the self-regulating WHA developed [6], which prevents mixing of the heated and heating carriers entering the battery from the charging and discharging circuits, is based on the natural stratification of water in the tank due to volumetric (Archimedes) forces in conditions of forced circulation (Figure 1). For this purpose, perforated supply pipes 1 and 3, and discharge pipes 2 and 4, are used, in which the area f of the holes 5 must be calculated according to conditions for ensuring distribution and selection of liquids from corresponding temperature layers, as well as stability of

stratification within the volume of the battery.

1. Perforated pipe for the supply of heating coolant. 2. Perforated discharge pipe for heated coolant.
3. Perforation of pipes for the supply and discharge of cooled heat. 4. Perforations in pipes for cooled and heated fluids. 5. Holes in the perforated pipes.

Fig.2. Schematic diagram of a self-regulating stratification heat accumulator

The effect of water stratification during short-term and long-term thermal accumulation can be determined from the dynamics of the solar system as a whole. In this regard, it depends on the type of thermal load covered by the system.

The latter was evaluated in [7, 8]. It was shown in [7] that the use of stratification in heating makes it possible to increase the share of SE use by 2-12%. A similar analysis carried out in [8] for hot water supply, heating, and air conditioning systems revealed an increase in the efficiency of solar systems when using water stratification in the storage tank by 5-15%.

In [9], based on the generalization of the test results of experimental solar houses with solar heating and cooling systems, it was shown that the use of stratification in short-term and long-term thermal accumulation leads to an increase in the use of solar heat by 15%. This conclusion is also confirmed by experimental data obtained in [10], according to which stratification increases the amount of usefully used radiation by 20%.

To optimally design stratification heat accumulators and properly design the storage system, it is necessary to understand the conditions under which stable stratification occurs and to assess its level. The stability of the stratified coolant flow within the battery volume, together with the Reynolds number, is significantly influenced by a dimensionless quantity known as the Richardson number [11].

$$Ri = -\frac{g}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dx} / \left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)_{st}^2 \quad (1)$$

The case $Ri = 0$ means a homogeneous liquid. The case $Ri > 0$ means a stable bundle. The case of $Ri < 0$ indicates an unstable bundle. In formula (1), the subscript "ct" means the velocity gradient value of the wall. Energy estimates show

[11] that turbulence decreases at $Ri > 2$. The stability limit is given as $Ri \geq 1$ in [11].

In the case of a continuous density distribution and with a linear velocity distribution in an infinitely distributed liquid, the value $Ri = 0.25$ is given as the stability limit in [11].

The differential equation, which was compiled for this case and describes the process of non-isothermal flow under the influence of volumetric forces (Figure 2), has the following form:

$$\overline{W}_x'' \overline{W}_x' + p \overline{W}_x' \overline{W}_x + q \overline{W}_x^2 = p Ri, \quad (2)$$

where $p = \mu^2 \bar{f}^2$; $q = -0,5 \mu^2 \bar{f}^2 \lambda \bar{l}$; $Ri = \frac{-gl \Delta \rho}{W_H^2 \rho}$; $\bar{f} = \frac{f}{F} = \frac{\delta l}{F}$; $\bar{l} = \frac{l}{d_s}$.

Boundary conditions: by $\left. \begin{matrix} \bar{x} = 0 & \overline{W}_0 = 0 \\ \bar{x} = 1 & \overline{W}_H = 1 \end{matrix} \right\} \quad (3)$

Fig. 2. Scheme of selective distribution of non-isothermal flow in the

The dimensionless Ri complex is a modified Richardson number that characterizes the ratio of Archimedes forces and inertial forces at the start of the water distribution system. In particular, $Ri=0.5$ means that these forces are equal. ($-gl\Delta\rho = 0,5\rho W_H^2$). If the Archimedes' forces are directed upwards ($\Delta\rho > 0$), that $Ri < 0$, otherwise, ($\Delta\rho < 0$), $Ri > 0$.

The determining value in the calculation of the water distribution is the parameter of the conditional gap. $\mu \bar{f}$. The value of the condition gap parameter that results in a flow rate of zero at one end of a water distribution system is known as the critical point. ($\mu \bar{f}^{kp}$), That is, when certain additional conditions are met, as shown in Figure 6:

$$Ri < 0,5 \quad \bar{v}_H = 0; \quad (4) \quad \text{or} \quad Ri > 0,5 \quad \bar{v}_0 = 0. \quad (5)$$

The differential equation (1), with boundary conditions (2) and additional conditions (3) and (4), was solved numerically using a PC and also analytically. $\lambda \bar{l} = 0$

, That is, for a short length of water distributor with smooth walls, an analytical expression has been obtained for the relative velocity of the flow inside the water distributor.

$$\bar{W}_{\bar{x}} = \sqrt{2Ri\bar{x} + \frac{2C_1}{p}} \sin \left[\pm \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{p} \left(\bar{x} + \frac{C_1}{pRi} \right) + \frac{C_2}{\sqrt{pRi\bar{x} + C_1}} \right], \quad (6)$$

CONCLUSIONS.

A self-regulating water heating system has been developed that uses temperature stratification to prevent the mixing of hot and cold water entering or leaving the system. This is achieved through the use of natural stratification forces such as Archimedes' force in a tank with forced circulation of a coolant. The system ensures that only hot water enters the heating circuit while cold water remains in the storage tank, preventing mixing and ensuring efficient heating.

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